

Use of cipher and cipher-key in carbohydrate nomenclature

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Abstract : The steric structures of the carbohydrates and related compounds have been concised and generalised through a proposed cipher and cipher-key to make the study easier.

Keywords : Carbohydrates, nomenclature and configuration, cipher and cipher-key.

Introduction

The essential stereochemical structure elucidation of carbohydrates belonging to the aldoses involved several useful and well-established prefixes¹. The Fischer projection is used and the CHO group (marked C₁) is set at the top, the CH₂OH at the bottom (C_n), the D/L-configurational notation is decided at the penultimate carbon (C_{n-1}), which is the starting point for setting configuration of aldoses [cf. D(+)-glyceraldehyde], and by applying the building up principle, larger aldoses are depicted in the D- or L-series. The OH group at C₂ of the first member of each pair is fixed on the right side of the D-series, which is the enantiomer of the L-series. Thus, the stereochemical structures of their aldoses are remembered by the mnemonic D-ARAlt GIAM-E; D-GuXI GaLyT-T, where the alphabets in higher case are the first letters of the prefixes¹, and the middlemen R, A, X and Ly are the aldopentoses generating each pair of aldohexoses. Moreover, anomeric notations (pyranose and furanose) are also well known terms.

But the nomenclature becomes complicated when the carbohydrate contains more than 4-asymmetric centers as well as C₁ generating anomeric center, represented by α-, β- in pyranose and furanose structures. Feldman in his noteworthy work² had designated methyl L-erythro-β-D-galacto-octopyranoside³ (IUPAC nomenclature, I) as methyl/36/-octopyranoside, which offers scope of further

simplification in the overall nomenclature of the carbohydrates. Two more examples such as, α-D-glucopyranosyl-β-D-fructofuranoside (II, cane sugar), and 4-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl-D-glucopyranose (III, lactose)⁴, may be cited which will clarify the usefulness of the proposed present cipher system.

[I]³

Methyl/36/-octopyranoside²

Methyl L-erythro-D-galacto-octopyranoside³

Cipher : [S^{VII}_{py}54(MeO i)]

[II]⁴

Cipher :

[R^V_{py}6]C₁-C₂[R^{IV}_{Ket(ii)Fu}2]

[III]⁴

Cipher : [R^V_{py}13]C₁-C₄[R^V_{py}14]

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Feldman introduced² the "Stereo Number" (Table 1 shows calculations) for short designation of the stereoisomers by utilizing binary numbers^{2,5-7}. In his opinion the "Octal Number" is even more advantageous than the binary numbers for structure elucidation of isomers.

Table 1. (Taking I as the example)

Column 1 (2 ⁿ)	Column 2	Column 3
64	0	0 × 64
32	1	1 × 32 = 32
16	0	0 × 16
8	0	0 × 8
4	1	1 × 4 = 4
2	0	0 × 2
1	0	0 × 1

Total "Stereo Number" = /36/;

So I is Methyl/36/-octopyranoside.

In column 1 powers of 2 are expressed, column 2 utilises Fischer projection with vertical backbone where all substituents on the left is assigned 0 (zero) and those on the right, 1 (one). The assignment starts from the lowest carbon (obviously the highest number) and the column 3 indicates the calculated "Stereo Number" which is attributed to the structure under consideration. Also in sugars, by convention, the α/β and D/L notations are given to the lowest and highest numbered asymmetric carbon atoms, respectively. A noteworthy report by McGinn and Wheatley⁷ indicates a combination of binary and decimal representations in carbohydrate nomenclature, which shows the necessity of further contemplation in this area. We wish to propose a new cipher-system mainly based on binary numbers vis-à-vis stereonumbers to designate each one of the carbohydrates, and to translate the stereonumber into stereostructure the cipher-key is utilized. The following sets are adopted during the presentation of this proposal.

Set (i). The following symbols are used to make the drawings quick and clean : O (CHO), A (CH₂OH), K (CO₂H), dash (-, OH), and C, H not shown in the Fischer projection with vertical backbone and putting the most oxidized carbon on the top, other functional groups (e.g. amino, halo etc.) are shown in their chemical formulae. Thus,

Set (ii). The highest numbered (i.e. ultimate) asymmetric center is specified by *R/S* notations. In case of *meso*-compounds, the *R/S* is replaced by "Mes". Thus :

Set (iii). The nearest two asymmetric centers when *cis*, (c), get zero and *trans*, (t) get one. The *c/t* notations start from the penultimate carbon, designated as *R/S* and 2^o starts from this carbon. These values are "n" in the binary numbers which are expanded like $n.2^0 + n.2^1 + n.2^2 + n.2^3 + n.2^4 + n.2^5 \dots$ etc. and the summation of the series giving the stereonumber. Therefore, when the configuration between the lowest two asymmetric centers is *t*, the stereo number of the compound will be always *odd*, (as $n.2^0 = 1$, in $t n = 1$), and this is the starting point for determining the stereo numbers.

Set (iv). Roman numerals, I, II, etc. (=x, in set vi) indicate the total number of asymmetric carbons in the molecule. The x will be the superscript in the cipher.

Set (v). The character (i.e. the chemical identity of the carbohydrate) is indicated as the subscript (=y). Examples of y are, Ald (aldose), Ari (aric acid), Gly (glycitol), Uro (uronic acid), Oni (onic acid), Py (pyranose ring), Fu (furanose ring), Ket (u) [in ketoses the keto group is located at u position]. Thus, Ket (ii) indicates that the keto group is at C₂ (u is expressed by i, ii, iiietc.). This keto group will hold the lowest possible locant [e.g. B (e)]. To avoid confusion the numerals are chosen to be of different classes, viz. Roman numerals (I, II etc. = x and i, ii, iii etc. = locant). Arabic

numerals (1, 2, etc. = stereo number = No in set vi) and locants of special group are as ii, iii etc.). The choice of all digits in Arabic numerals is avoided for the sake of easy understanding of the cipher.

Set (vi). The stereo number (=No), derived in set (iii) will determine the configuration of the given carbohydrate and the combined set (i) through (vi) will constitute the cipher of the compound. Thus, the general cipher, shown below, illustrates the following characteristics of the molecule.

Set (vii). In case of *meso* compounds the *R/S* is replaced by *Mes* (*meso*). If heteroatoms other than oxygen are directly attached to the backbone, the same cipher rule will follow and the locants of the heteroatoms (e.g. in amino, thio, halo etc.) will be shown as i, ii etc. in the alphabetic order. The absence of OH on the carbon holding the heteroatom will be indicated by "Des". The higher priority group (as per CIP system) in such case will be equivalent to OH group and will get preference.

Set (viii). If the optical rotation of the compound is known it can be designated by d or l in parenthesis, e.g. (l) $[R^{II}_{Ald}0]$ or (d) $[R^{III}_{Ald}3]$ for D(-)-erythrose and D(+)-xylose respectively.

Examples.

[A] Aldoses :

(a)

Explanation : C_3 is the highest numbered chiral center which is of *R*-configuration. The superscript II shows

two asymmetric centers (C_2 and C_3), and the subscript Ald indicates aldose in Fischer projection (CHO at C_1). The stereo number 0 (zero) indicates the *cis* configuration between C_2 and C_3 . $[S^{II}_{Ald}0]$ is its enantiomer and $[R^{II}_{Ald}1]$ and $[S^{II}_{Ald}1]$ are its diastereoisomers.

(b)

The stereo number will be between zero and $2^{n-1}-1$ where n is the number of asymmetric carbons.

(c) Thus,

Hexose epimeric pairs :

$[R^{IV}_{Ald}6]$: D(+)-Glucose and $[R^{IV}_{Ald}2]$: D(+)-Mannose

$[R^{IV}_{Ald}0]$: D(+)-Allose and $[R^{IV}_{Ald}4]$: D(+)-Altrose

$[R^{IV}_{Ald}3]$: D(-)-Gulucose and $[R^{IV}_{Ald}7]$: D(-)-Idose

So, it is evident that stereo numbers 0, 2, 4 and 6 have *cis*-configuration at the lowest two asymmetric centers, and 1, 3, 5 and 7 have *trans*-configuration at the lowest two asymmetric centers. The stereo numbers range between 0 and 7 (i.e. $2^{n-1}-1$, where n is the number of asymmetric centers, IV, in the present examples). Interestingly, the stereo number difference between each hexose epimeric pair is 4. Therefore, when the names of the aldoses are unknown, their stereoisomers can be drawn from the ciphers utilising the cipher-keys. An apposite example is given below by selecting an aldose having cipher $[S^{VI}_{Ald}19]$.

Procedure : (i) Since the given compound is an aldose (subscript Ald), the Fischer projection with vertical backbone will hold the CHO (i.e. O) at the top and the CH_2OH (i.e. A) at the bottom.

(ii) The roman numeral VI indicates that the molecule has VI (i.e. 6) + 2 (C_1 and C_6) = 8 carbons of which six carbons are chiral.

(iii) The highest numbered chiral carbon (i.e. the lowest position, C₇) is of *S*-configuration.

(iv) Since the stereo number is odd (i.e. 19), the configuration between lowest two carbons (C₆ and C₇) is *trans*.

(v) The stereo number 19 splits into 1+2+0+0+16 [corresponding to $n \cdot 2^0 + n \cdot 2^1 + n \cdot 2^2 + n \cdot 2^3 + n \cdot 2^4$ (corresponding to 6 chiral centers, and putting $n=0$ for *cis* and $n=1$ for *trans*)]. It fits with the arrangement *t, t, c, c, t* for (a). The last *t* stands for the *trans* configuration between C₆ and C₇, thus contributing 1 to make the stereo number odd. The $n \cdot 2^x$ should be as close as possible to the stereo numbers (starting or residual).

(vi) Finally, the stereo structure of the given cipher is drawn (a) from the above-mentioned cipher-key.

Therefore, the stereo numbers of compounds containing n chiral centers will range between 0 (all *cis*) and $2^{n-1}-1$ (all *trans*).

[B] Ketoses : The locations of the keto groups are expressed as (ii, iii etc.). The locant should be lowest. Thus, Ket (ii) is keto group at C₂.

Looks like 4-keto compound This is 3-keto compound
This is [R^{III}_{Ket(ii)}1] not [R^{III}_{Ket(ii)}2]

[C] Miscellaneous examples :

(i) Alditols (ii) Ketoses (keto group at central C)

In general, it may be mentioned that the lowest 'Stereo Number' gets maximum priority in denoting the cipher.

(iii) Amino acids (smaller stereo number is given) (iv) Meso acids

(v) Onic acids (vi) Uronic acids

(vii) Keto-amic acids (viii) Keto-onic acids (ix) Keto-uronic acids

(x) Des (desoxy or deoxy) : OH on backbone if replaced by H or any heteroatom, is indicated by Des i, ii etc. where i, ii etc. are locations of such H or heteroatom.

(i) Replacement of OH by H :

(ii) By heteroatoms : (Greater atomic number is equivalent to OH group)

(xi) (a) D-Glucopyranose (α - and β -) and (b) D-Fructofuranose

(xii) Pyranosides and pyranose derivatives

[D] Disaccharides : In the following are given the common names (nomenclature and cipher of a few representatives).

- (i) Cane sugar, (vide II), [cipher].
- (ii) Lactose, (vide III), [cipher].
- (iii) Maltose⁴, (4-O- α -D-Glucopyranosyl-D-glucopyranose), $[R^V_{Py}6]C_1-C_4[R^V_{Py}6]$: The α -anomer.
- (iv) Cellobiose⁴, (4-O- β -D-Glucopyranosyl-D-glucopyranose), $[R^V_{Py}14]C_1-C_4[R^V_{Py}14]$: The β -anomer.
- (v) Melibiose⁴, $[R^V_{Py}5]C_1-C_6[R^V_{Py}14]$: The β -anomer.
- (vi) Gentiobiose⁴, $[R^V_{Py}14]C_1-C_6[R^V_{Py}14]$: The β -anomer.

[E] Trisaccharides :

- (i) Raffinose⁴, $[R^V_{Py}5]C_1-C_6[R^V_{Py}6]C_1-C_2[R^V_{Ket(ii)Fu}2]$.
- (ii) Gentianose⁴, $[R^V_{Py}14]C_1-C_6[R^V_{Py}6]C_1-C_2[R^{IV}_{Ket(ii)Fu}2]$.

[F] Polysaccharides : (x is very large number).

- (i) Cellulose⁴, $[R^V_{Py}14]C_1-(C_4[R^V_{Py}14]C_1-C_4[R^V_{Py}14]C_1)_x-C_4[R^V_{Py}14\ or\ 6]$.
- (ii) Starch⁴, $[R^V_{Py}6]C_1-(C_4[R^V_{Py}6]C_1-C_4[R^V_{Py}6]C_1)_x-C_4[R^V_{Py}14\ or\ 6]$.

Conclusion :

In spite of the well-known and accepted IUPAC Nomenclature of carbohydrates, which still uses the trivial names of monosaccharides like erythrose, arabinose, glucose etc. and the other existing systems, the present manuscript deals with a more concised yet simplified, general and readily understandable method of carbohydrate nomenclature, avoiding trivial names of the monosaccharides, making the structure-nomenclature inter-conversion of carbohydrates much easier. It is contemplated that the cipher-key would be helpful to draw the configurational structures of the carbohydrates when the corresponding cipher is available and vice-versa.

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